

IMPACT OF CROPSAP SCHEME ON COTTON GROWERS : A PROBIT REGRESSION APPROACH

Vaishali G. Kogade 1*, R. V. Chavan 2, S. V. Bharti 3

1* M.Sc. student, 2 Associate Professor and 3 Teaching associate,
Department of Agricultural Economics, College of Agriculture, Parbhani, (M.S)

* Corresponding author's email: vaishalikogde99@gmail.com

(MS Received: 26.11.2023; MS Revised:30.12.2023; MS Accepted:01.01.2024)

MS 3141

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS)

10.5281/zenodo.10473123

Abstract

In the present study economic impact of CROPSAP scheme on beneficiary and non-beneficiary cotton growers have been assessed. This was based mainly on primary data which was collected through personal interview method with the help of pre-tested schedules. An investigation was conducted in the Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar district of Maharashtra state purposively on the basis of highest area under cotton crop. Multistage sampling technique was used for selection of district, tehsils and villages. Total sample size was 160 where 80 was beneficiary and 80 non-beneficiary cotton growers. Probit regression model was fitted to access the impact of CROPSAP scheme on beneficiary and non-beneficiary cotton growers. Probit model is a way to perform regression for binary outcome variable with two possibilities like beneficiary and non-beneficiary of cotton growers. In probit regression model factors like X_4 (Plant protection under CROPSAP) and X_6 (Yield) significant at 10 per cent and 5 per cent level respectively. This result indicates that the above significant factors are greatly influenced on cotton growers towards adoption of CROPSAP scheme.

Keywords: Cotton, beneficiary and non-beneficiary, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar, CROPSAP scheme, Probit model etc.

Introduction

Cotton is one of the most important commercial crop cultivated in India and accounts for around 25% of the total global cotton production. Cotton, Genus *Gossypium* belongs to the family malvaceae and includes in all 35 species. It is said to have two centers of origin of cotton in which one is the old world viz., India, Indonesia and Tropical Africa while the other is the New World viz., Mexico or Central America. The word cotton is derived from the Arabic word "Qutn". Generally four cotton species are grown namely *Gossypium arboreum*, *Gossypium hirsutum*, *Gossypium barbadense* and *Gossypium herbaceum*, (Salihu and Singh, 2020). India is having 1st place in the world with estimated production of 362.18 lakh bales (6.16 Million Metric Tonnes during cotton season 2021-22 i.e., 23% of world cotton production of 1555 lakh bales (26.44 Million Metric Tonnes). India is also the 2nd largest consumer of cotton in the world with estimated consumption of 338 lakh bales (5.75 Million Metric Tonnes i.e. 22% of world cotton consumption of 1507 lakh bales (25.63 Million Metric Tonnes). In Maharashtra major cotton growing districts are namely Aurangabad, Jalna, Beed, Parbhani, Nanded, Hingoli, Latur, Osmanabad in Marathwada region while Akola, Amaravati, Buldhana, Chandrapur, Dhule, Jalgaon, Nagpur, Wardha, and Yavatmal in Vidarbha region. Marathwada region contributes an area of 1.07 million hectares (11.89 per cent) with annual production of 0.14 million tonnes of lint (0.75 million bales). Cotton is dominantly grown under rainfed condition in the region. The Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar district is one of the leading districts in cotton cultivation.

During 2008-09, there was a severe pest outbreak of *Spodoptera litura* L. (Fabricius) coupled with *Helicoverpa armigera* L. (Hubner) and other leaf eating caterpillars in cotton-soybean based cropping system. Such a preventive action required a strong pest monitoring and advisory mechanism to be put in place. A series of meetings were held between March and May 2009 amongst the team of scientists of Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR) crop based institutes and State Agricultural Universities (SAUS) of Maharashtra with State Agriculture Department of Maharashtra to develop the modalities of the programme including the area of operation, roles and responsibilities of different stakeholders, and preparation of project document for funding under Rashtriya Krishi Vikas Yojana (RKVY) by the Commissionerate of Agriculture, Government of Maharashtra. The State Agriculture Department of Maharashtra is the CROPSAP implementation authority with the funding through RKVY of Central Government till 2012 followed by Government of Maharashtra from 2013 till date, (Nand *et al.*, 2022). There are very few studies were conducted on CROPSAP scheme so goal of present study is to test whether CROPSAP scheme strikes positively on cotton growers.

Methodology

Multistage sampling design was used for present study. In the first stage, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar district was selected purposively from Marathwada region on the basis of highest area under cotton crop. The district contributes area about 4070.43 ha, 5649.42 tonnes production, 238.27 kg/ha productivity. In the second stage, from each selected district, five tehsils namely, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar, Paithan, Gangapur, Sillod and Phumbri were selected. In the third stage, four villages were selected from each tehsil. In the fourth stage, 4 beneficiary and 4 non-beneficiary cotton growers were selected. Thus, total sample size from 20 villages was 160, out of which 80 beneficiary and 80 non-beneficiary cotton growers, (Kiresur and Ichangi, 2011). The data were collected through personal interview method with the help of pre-tested schedule.

Analytical tools

Probit regression model was fitted to access the impact of CROPSAP scheme on beneficiary and non-beneficiary cotton growers. Probit model is a way to perform regression for binary outcome variable with two possibilities like beneficiary and non-beneficiary of cotton growers. (Sadashivappa, 2015) The probit regression is given as,

$$Y_{it} = \beta X_{it} + (q_i + \mu_i) + \mu_{it}$$

Where Y = Dependent variable

X = Independent variable

μ_i = Error term

β = Coefficient of regression

Results and discussion

The study was undertaken with view to study the economic impact of CROPSAP scheme on beneficiary and non-beneficiary cotton growers in Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar district of Maharashtra state.

A probit regression model designed to analyze response variables with only two outcomes (Freedman, 2009) was used to describe the impact of CROPSAP scheme on cotton growers. Where some factors such as X_1 , X_2 , X_3 , X_4 , X_5 , X_6 are used to describe sowing time, spacing, plant population, plant protection practices under CROPSAP, insecticides and fungicides and yield respectively are responsible factors for increasing the attitude of farmers towards adoption of CROPSAP scheme. The result of probit regression model was given in table 3.1. where X_4 (Plant protection under CROPSAP) and X_6 (Yield) were significantly associated with probability of CROPSAP scheme affected positively on cotton growers. Where X_4 (Plant protection under CROPSAP) and X_6 (Yield) significant at 10 per cent and 5 per cent level respectively. Similar results obtained by Kimbi (2021) for adoption of improved sorghum technologies among farmers in Tanzania. Hence this result indicates that the above significant factors are greatly influenced on cotton growers towards adoption of CROPSAP scheme. The above result indicates that the proper spacing and use of plant protection recommended by CROPSAP helps to increase the yield and reduce the overuse of plant protection.

Table 3.1. Results of Probit regression model

Sr.No.	Factors	Coefficient	Standard error
1	Sowing time	-0.004	8.48
2	Spacing	0.005	1.37
3	Plant population	0.001	0.179
4	Plant protection practices under CROPSAP scheme	1.398***	2.38
5	Insecticides and Pesticides	0.036	4.61
6	Yield	1.27**	1.09

Note : ** significant at 5 per cent level, *** significant at 10 per cent level

Conclusion

In probit regression model factors like X₄ (Plant protection under CROPSAP) and X₆ (Yield) significant at 10 per cent and 5 per cent level respectively. Hence this result indicates that the above significant factors are greatly influenced on cotton growers towards adoption of CROPSAP scheme. The above result indicates that the proper spacing and use of plant protection recommended by CROPSAP helps to increase the yield and reduce the overuse of plant protection. From above results it was concluded that the Government, NGO's, and other Agricultural organizations has to take appropriate actions to aware the farmers community regarding importance of CROPSAP scheme to increase their yield.

References

- Ambhure Akash Laxman*; Swati Suman *; Syed H. Mazhar 2022 ***"Constraints Faced By Bt Cotton Growers In Adoption Of Drip Irrigation System And Itsmanagement Practices In Parbhani District Of Maharashtra." Vol. Xii, Issue Xxxiii, July 2022, Multilogic In Science, ISSN 2277-7601, Page 159-160.
- A.S. Latkar*, A.N. Surpam and P.V. Yadgirwar 2022 "Productivity Of Bt Cotton Based Cropping System In Central Vidarbha Zone Of Maharashtra" Vol. Xiii, Issue Xxxviii, Oct 2023, Multilogic In Science, ISSN 2277-7601, Page 1005-1006.
- Barre Jyothsna Priyadarshini*1, D. K. Sinha1, Nasim Ahmed1, K. M. Singh1, Mahesh Kumar2, S. P. Singh3 2022 "Constraints Perceived By The Cotton Growers In Bhadradi Kothagudem District Of Telangana" Vol. Xii, Issue Xxxii, April 2022 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, Page 14-17
- Bennett, R. M., Ismael, Y., Morse, S., & Kambhampati, U. S. (2004). Economic impact of genetically modified cotton in India. *AgBioForum*, 7(3): 96-100
- Choudhary, B., & Gaur, K. (2010). Bt cotton in India: A country profile. *ISAAA Series of Biotech Crop Profiles*. ISAAA: Ithaca, NY. 978-1-892456-46-X
- D.R. Nikam1 and D.D. Pawar2 2022 "Comparative Economics Of Cotton Cultivation Under Micro-Irrigation System In North Maharashtra" Vol. Xii, Issue Xxxii, April 2022, Multilogic In Science, ISSN 2277-7601, Page 29-33.
- Freedman, D. A. (2009). *Statistical models: Theory and Practice*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK
- Hardik S. Lad*, H. R. Ramani, M. D. Khunt And N. B. Pansuriya 2022 "Effect Of Different Level Of Sulphur On Biochemical Characters Of Cotton (*Gossypiumhirsutum* L.)" Vol. Xii, Issue Xxxii, April 2022, Multilogic In Science, ISSN 2277-7601,Page 18-22.
- Kamble, B. T., Navadkar, D. S., & Yadav, D. (20). Impact assessment of adopted cotton production technology and constraints in Marathwada Region Of Maharashtra State. *Gujarat Journal Of Extension Education*, 22(2), 209- 214.
- Kimbi, T. G., Essegbemon, A., Kongola, E., Chris O. Ojiewo, Ronnie, V., Muricho, G., Ringo, J., Gerald, A. L., Varshney, R., & Tabo, R. (2021). A probit analysis of determinants of adoption of improved sorghum technologies among farmers in tanzania. *Journal of Agricultural Science*, 13(1), 1916-9760.
- Kiresur, V. R., & Ichangi, M. (2011). Socio-economic impact of Bt cotton- A casestudy of Karnataka. *Agricultural Economics Research Review*, 24(1), 67-81.
- Kuruganti, K. (2009). Bt cotton and the myth of enhanced yields. *Economic and Political Weekly*,40(4) 29- 33.
- kamera. Aditya, 2dr. Sanjay Kumar 2022"An Economic Analysis Of Bt Cotton Production In Manchirial District, Telangana." Vol. Xii, Issue Xxxiii, July 2022, Multilogic In Science, Issn 2277-7601, Page 141-143.
- Micha Hima Bindu, Mukesh Maurya, 1Ravi S C, Avinash Mishra 2022 "An Economic Analysis Of Cotton Production In Bhadradi Kothagudem District Of Telanganastate." Vol. Xii, Issue Xxxiii, July 2022, Multilogic In Science, ISSN 2277-7601, Page 31-35.
- Morse, S., Bennett, R., & Ismael, Y. (2006). Environmental impact of genetically modified cotton in South Africa. *Agriculture, ecosystems & environment*, 117(4), 277-289.
- Nand, S., Jakkawad, S. R., & Deshmukh, N.D.(2022). Constraints faced by beneficiary farmers in 'crop pest surveillance and advisory project' and suggestions to overcome the constraints. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 11(12), 4177-4179.
- Raju M. Gavhane, S.K.Bhalkare*, P.P. Patil and D.B. Undirwade 2022 "Itk Components For The Management Of Aphids And Leaf Hoppers In Bt Cotton"Vol. Xii, Issue Xxxii, April 2022, Multilogic In Science, ISSN 2277-7601, Page 98-100.
- Rao, N. C., & Dev, S. M. (2009). Socio-economic Impact of Transgenic Cotton. *Agricultural Economics Research Review*, 22(conf), 461-470.
- Sabir, H. M., Tahir, S. H., & Khan, M. B. (2011). Bt cotton and its impact on cropping pattern in Punjab. *Pak J Soc Sci*, 31(1), 127-134.
- Sadashivappa, P. (2015). Socio-economic impacts of Bt cotton adoption in India: Evidence from panel data. *AgBioForum*, 18(2) 193-208
- Salihu and Singh (2020) examined the Cotton Production and Socio-economic Characteristics of cotton Farmers in Maharashtra, India. *Journal of Environmental Issues and Agriculture*, 12(1), 2141-2731.
- V. G. Arude1*, S. K. Shukla2 and S. S. Kautkar3 2022"Adoption And Assessment Of Suitability Of Seed Cotton Contamination Cleaner Forcontamination Control In Indian Ginning Industry"Vol. Xii, Issue Xxxiv, Oct 2022, Multilogic In Science, Issn 2277-7601, Page 310-313.
- Wagan, S. A., Memon, Q. U. A., Tan, Y., Damalas, C. A., Memon, A., Sheikh, M. J., & Khushk, G. M. (2023). Farmers' knowledge of pests and decision for pesticide selection in cotton: impact on productionefficiency levels in southern Pakistan. *International Journal of Pest Management*, 1- 10.
- Yadav, S., Godara, A. K., & Yadav, V. P. S. (2018). Impact of Bt cotton production technology in Haryana. *Indian Research Journal of Extension Education*, 18(2), 66-71.